

Language Anxiety among APESA Students in Morocco: An Exploratory Analysis

Imad Messouab

*Department of Languages and Communication, Hassan II Institute
of Agronomy and Veterinary Medicine, Morocco*

Anouar Mohamed El Kasri

Department of English Studies, Moulay Ismail University, Morocco

Abdelaziz Ouchaib

Department of English Studies, Moulay Ismail University, Morocco

Abstract

Foreign language anxiety is a significant factor affecting students' oral production. That is, anxiety for EFL students is considered the most frightening language skill. This article is twofold. It endeavors to identify the factors that make APESA students anxious about their communication and participation in the classroom (Année Préparatoire aux Etudes Supérieures en Agriculture). Also, it will suggest some interventions or strategies that can be used to reduce students' communication anxiety. 222 freshman students participated in the study by filling out an online questionnaire, based on Horwitz's foreign language classroom anxiety scales, distributed during the session to account for the research objectives. The results of the study indicated that communication apprehension (the fear of speaking in front of the public) is the first factor that causes language anxiety among APESA students. Then, students' linguistic competency came as the second factor. The study's results can be useful for instructors and students as well by presenting and suggesting some pedagogical keys to lock this issue of language anxiety in the EFL context.

Keywords: *APESA students, foreign language Anxiety (FLA), English, fear of speaking, pedagogical intervention.*

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Introduction

Overview of Language Anxiety among APESA Students in Morocco

This study aims to address language anxiety among APESA students in Morocco by exploring factors such as cultural influences, language barriers, and academic pressures. Through a questionnaire, the present study will identify interventions and strategies to

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help students overcome this challenge, ultimately improving their overall well-being and academic success by addressing this often-neglected issue.

This study is different from most of the consulted ones because of its targeted highly qualified students. The study deals with freshman students (future engineers in agriculture and veterinary medicine) with perfect grades at their Baccalaureate; 17 and 18 out of 20 (good or very good). Their English levels are between B1 and C1 according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) based on a diagnostic test conducted at the beginning of the course. However, it can be challenging to determine whether a lack of motivation or FLA is responsible for students' reluctance to engage in speaking activities in the classroom. The study is organized into three sections. The first reviews the most significant studies on FLA in the EFL context. The second section outlines the study methodology adopted for the study. The final one presents the study's results, recommendations, and conclusion.

Importance of Addressing Language Anxiety in Academic Settings

It is imperative to address language anxiety in academic settings due to its significant impact on student's overall well-being and academic success. Language anxiety can lead to feelings of isolation, low self-esteem, and even depression, making it difficult for students to engage in their studies and participate in classroom activities fully. Furthermore, students grappling with language anxiety may face challenges in establishing connections with their peers and professors, which can significantly impede their academic advancement. By addressing this issue and providing targeted support, educators and professionals or experts can aid students in overcoming their language anxiety and thriving in their academic pursuits.

Literature Review

Language Anxiety in EFL: A Review of Theoretical Foundations and Empirical Findings

This section focuses on the consulted literature surrounding anxiety in the context of EFL. Language anxiety can be expressed by students who appear less willing to take part in any discussion in the classroom due to many internal and external factors. For decades, researchers have investigated students' anxiety in second language acquisition (SLA) due to its significant influence on their academic performance and overall career development. The results from these studies highlight the critical role that anxiety plays in the language learning process, affecting not only students' motivation and engagement but also their success in mastering a new language.

The issue of anxiety for EFL students has been investigated by many researchers (Horwitz et al. 1986, 2001; Von Worde, 2003; Matsuda & Gobel, 2004, among others). They found that speaking is the most frightening skill (stage fright). It is said that when anxious students try to participate in the classroom, they feel nervous, frightened, reluctant, shaking and sweating and sometimes their hearts beat quickly (start to freeze). According to MacIntyre & Gardner (1991), FLA is fear or apprehension when a student is expected to use a second or foreign language. There is a consensus among researchers that FLA harms short- and long-term memory, therefore slowing down their motivation and learning process and boosting their nervousness and worries. That is, many anxious students associate the classroom context with a place of discomfort, fear and reluctance.

Causes of Language Anxiety

Researchers have suggested many theories to elaborate on what causes language anxiety, what variables may affect it, and more importantly, how to cope with it (Cooper et al., 2018; Horwitz et al. 1986). Researchers have found numerous causes that contribute to the development of students' FLA, such as past negative experiences, low self-confidence, fear of judgment, and perfectionism (Atifnigar, 2024; Faqih, 2023; Yalçın, & İnceçay, 2014). For instance, a student who has received harsh criticism from a teacher might become afraid to speak up in class, resulting in decreased participation and missed learning opportunities. Additionally, students who struggle with perfectionism may feel immense pressure to always have the perfect answer, causing them to avoid speaking altogether for fear of making a mistake. To cover this issue from a wide view, Horwitz et al. (1986) proposed three key elements that surround FLA. The first one is "communication apprehension (CA)" also referred to as "stage fright", which is the fear of speaking with or in front of people (glossophobia). In this regard, Horwitz et al. (1986, p. 127) claim that "people who typically have trouble speaking in groups are likely to experience even greater difficulty speaking in a foreign language class where they have little control of the communicative situation and their performance is constantly monitored." The second cause is "test anxiety (TA) or apprehension over academic performance", which is the fear of failure, especially in oral tests or quizzes. Students with a TA most of the time establish unattainable objectives and strive for flawless performance, leading to elevated anxiety levels. The last one is named the fear of negative evaluation (FNE). As the name implies, it means that anxious students are afraid of being judged or evaluated by others (teachers, peers, or colleagues). Students might feel nervous in situations such as oral exams, quizzes, presentations, or answering questions. They assume that their colleagues will laugh at them because of their insufficient language skills or abilities.

Moreover, it is worth stating that students' cultural background is a significant factor that affects their communication directly or indirectly due to unfamiliarity with cultural norms and communication styles. To support this claim, Messouab (2022) conducted a study on barriers to oral communication among university students in Morocco. His results indicated that social and cultural factors are the primary barriers preventing students from participating in classroom interactions with their instructors.

Anxiety and students' achievement

In the EFL context, language anxiety among students is a significant variable that affects their achievement directly or indirectly. It is worthy to make a distinction between positive (helpful) and negative (harmful) anxiety. The former one, in language learning, improves language performance. That is, a specific degree of anxiety is thought to enhance performance, indicating the existence of an ideal level of anxiety. The latter, on the other hand, affects students' performance negatively. In this way, Horwitz et al. (1986), stated that "negative anxiety may play a crucial role in preventing language learners from communicating effectively". Moreover, language anxiety has been shown to have cognitive, physical, emotional, and social signs. For example, FLA, from MacIntyre's view (2002), has cognitive effects, such as disruptions in thinking and reasoning; social effects, including avoidance of communication with others; and personal effects, exemplified by learners' underestimation of themselves.

Materials and Methods

Introduction

To explore the causes influencing communication anxiety for APESA students, A quantitative method is used through an online questionnaire based on Horwitz's foreign language classroom anxiety scales (with nuance modification to meet the study's objectives) that are distributed to gather data on the prevalence of language anxiety and its effect on students' achievement. This section includes the purpose of the study, Research questions, statement of the problem, sampling techniques, participants, data analysis procedures, and a conclusion.

Purpose of the study

The presented study aims to identify the factors that make APESA students anxious about their language use and participation in the classroom. Specifically, we seek to investigate the prevalence of FLA among students, the contributing factors to its development, and the possible pedagogical interventions to mitigate students' language anxiety. Unlike many studies conducted in Morocco, which focus on university students with average language performance, this study examines highly competent students in their academic careers. It aims to evaluate whether language anxiety is solely linked to linguistic shortcomings or if other factors contribute to it.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide our investigation:

- 1- What are the factors that trigger language anxiety among APESA students?
- 2-What specific interventions or strategies can help reduce language anxiety among APESA students?

Statement of the Problem

FLA is a common issue among students, particularly those who lack competency in English language learning. It is often linked most of the time with fear, discomfort, shyness and apprehension in spoken interactions. This anxiety can significantly impair language learning and participation in class discussions. Despite its impact on students' speaking skills and maybe other skills, there is limited research proposing useful interventions to help students overcome this challenge. Being abreast of the causes, effects, and potential strategies for language anxiety is essential to support students' academic success and overall well-being.

Sampling Techniques

A quantitative research design was employed to fulfill the study's objectives. The study used convenience sampling by recruiting 222 first-year APESA students (future engineering in agronomy and veterinary medicine). Data was collected via an online questionnaire, which was distributed during a planned session. This sampling technique enables the collection of responses from a broad and varied cohort within the program, facilitating an in-depth investigation of anxiety-related factors affecting students' oral production and classroom participation. The chosen methodology aligns with the study's objectives to identify primary anxiety triggers and evaluate the prevalence of communication apprehension within this specific student group.

Participants

The study involved 222 freshmen from APESA who participated voluntarily. The sample consisted of 70% Females and 30% males, with ages varying between 17 and 21 years old. Their English proficiency levels, determined through a diagnostic test conducted at the beginning of the course, ranged from B1 to C1 according to CEFR. They filled out the questionnaire in approximately five minutes in the classroom either using phones or laptops.

Data Analysis Procedures

Data was gathered through an online questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means and standard of deviations). To investigate the factors that make APESA students anxious, inferential analyses were undertaken to examine particular anxiety triggers and to uncover correlations between anxiety levels and factors such as past linguistic experience. These methodologies facilitated a comprehensive comprehension of the fundamental roots of language anxiety, guiding the study's recommendations for educational solutions.

Conclusion

The methodology offered a comprehensive framework for identifying primary anxiety triggers and their effects on students' language performance and participation. This analytical approach facilitates the study's objective of providing specific insights and solutions for alleviating language anxiety throughout the APESA program. This study employed a quantitative methodology utilizing an online questionnaire structured in Horwitz's modified foreign language classroom anxiety measures to examine factors causing language anxiety among APESA students.

Results

This section will present the results of the study in response to the study's objectives; focusing on the factors that contribute to language anxiety among APESA students and the potential strategies to alleviate it. To address the first research question, especially the first one, a combination of descriptive statistics was conducted, such as exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to identify latent constructs causing anxiety and descriptive statistics (means, frequencies and standard of deviations) to summarize anxiety levels while a correlation analysis can assess the relationship between anxiety and other factors (variables).

Table1. Factors that Trigger Language Anxiety among APESA Students

What are some reasons that prevent you from participating in the classroom?	%
I feel nervous speaking in front of my classmates	25,7
My linguistic competence is not good enough	25,2
I am not confident that my English skills are not sufficient enough	14,4
I am afraid of being judged by my colleagues or by my professor	20,3
I am not self-confidence	10,9
I feel intimidated by the professor	2,8
Fear of Negative Evaluation of them	2,7
All of the above reasons	0,9
None of them, I feel comfortable in the classroom	21,6

The results in Table 1 indicate factors that block students from participating in the classroom. The most significant factor is nervousness while speaking in front of classmates or communication apprehension (CA) which represents 25.7%, closely followed by inadequate linguistic competence with 25.2%. Fear of being judged by peers or professors is another prevalent concern with 20.3%, whereas limited self-confidence affects 10.9% of respondents. Poor English skills impede participation for 14.4%, indicating that language and confidence issues play a critical role. Notably, intimidation by professors 2.8% and fear of negative evaluations 2.7% are the least cited reasons, showing that authority figures are less frequently perceived as participation barriers. Only 0.9% attributes their lack of participation to all the listed reasons, while a significant proportion of 21.6% feel entirely comfortable in the classroom, indicating no such anxiety, especially girls.

Asking students about how often they feel shy to participate in the classroom is a key element to cover more data about the research objectives. 9.5% reported that they feel shy all the time, 64.9 sometimes and 24.8 said that they do not have this problem.

The mean is roughly 2.14, suggesting that the average response aligns more closely with "Sometimes" on the ordinal scale. The standard deviation (SD) is about 0.60, indicating modest variety in the answers, with the majority of the participants clustering around "Sometimes."

The mean of 2.14 suggests that, on average, respondents demonstrate shyness in classroom participation, aligning more closely with the (Sometimes) category, implying that occasional shyness is prevalent among students. On the other hand, SD of 0.60 indicates substantial variability, suggesting that although most students are categorized as (Sometimes), there is a significant dispersion in their replies. A minority of students continuously experience shyness (Always), whereas others seldom encounter it (Never). The comparatively low average indicates that shyness is a persistent albeit manageable concern, implying the necessity for focused treatments to tackle sporadic feelings of unease or reluctance in classroom engagement.

Another question targeted students was "I feel anxious when speaking in front of my classmates during class discussions". The mean stills 2.59, which suggests responses, are slightly inclined towards "Disagree" but close to neutral and the SD remains 0.89. This means that among 220 students, the majority (88 students) selected "Neutral," signifying a lack of extreme anxiety or complete comfort while addressing other students. A substantial percentage (65 students) opposed the assertion, indicating that a sizable segment did not experience anxiety. Nevertheless, 38 students concurred, signifying that worry persists as a significant issue for certain individuals. The absence of students selecting "Strongly Agree" indicates that extreme anxiety is not prevalent. The results demonstrate that although the classroom setting seems encouraging, implementing measures to alleviate mild to moderate anxiety might enhance the group's experience.

Furthermore, students' answers to the question "My language anxiety negatively impacts my academic performance during oral presentations or class discussions" showed that the largest response category is "disagree" (64 students), followed closely by "agree" (56 students) and "neutral" (54 students). This distribution indicates a division of opinions, with a minor inclination towards dissent regarding the assertion that language anxiety negatively impacts my academic achievement. The lack of "strongly agree" answers indicates that extreme anxiety is not prevalent in this setting. The SD of 0.98 signifies variability in viewpoints, suggesting that fear may still

considerably affect a portion of students. These findings indicate the necessity for supporting measures to alleviate anxiety during oral presentations or conversations for the afflicted individuals.

Table 2. Students Fear of Making Mistakes

I do not participate in the classroom because I feel afraid of making mistakes.	%
1 Strongly disagree	18,9
2 Disagree	30,6
3 Neutral	24,3
4 Agree	27
5 Strongly agree	0

Data in Table 2 indicates that the fear of making mistakes among students has a substantial impact on their classroom participation. The statement that fear of making mistakes prevents their participation is controversial among the 222 participants, with 18.9% firmly disagreeing and 30.6% disagreeing. This indicates that the majority (49.5%) do not regard this fear as a primary barrier. Nevertheless, 27% of students agree, while 24.3% are uncertain, suggesting that this apprehension does indeed restrict their participation for a significant portion of students. It is important to note that no respondents selected "strongly agree," indicating that this issue is not overwhelmingly prevalent but still prevalent enough to warrant attention.

The mean response of approximately 2.59 suggests that students have a slight tendency toward disagreement, although responses are clustered around "neutral." The SD is around 0.98 indicating moderate variability in perceptions, emphasizing that while fear of mistakes may not universally impede participation, it substantially impacts specific individuals. The balance between agreement and disagreement indicates individual differences in confidence levels and comfort in classroom contexts.

From an academic perspective, these results highlight the significance of establishing learning environments that are both supportive and non-judgmental. Although the majority of students do not appear to be affected by fear of making mistakes, targeted interventions—including the promotion of a growth mindset, the provision of constructive feedback, and the recognition of errors as a natural part of the learning process—have the potential to alleviate anxiety for the 27% of students who concur with the statement and to engage those who are neutral. By addressing this issue, it may be possible to increase the overall participation percentages and improve the inclusivity of classroom dynamics.

As a conclusion to the results of the presented study, we can deduce that communication apprehension and students' linguistic competency are the main factors causing language anxiety among APESA students or influencing their participation in speaking activities. Although some students feel confident in communication, many others still struggle with fear and apprehension of judgment. This underscores the significance of supportive environments that foster active engagement and reduce anxiety. Inclusivity and participation can be enhanced through strategies such as promoting a growth mindset and accepting mistakes as a natural part of the learning process. The next section will present some interventions or strategies to alleviate the issue of language anxiety among students.

Recommendations

The study's second research question was about suggesting pedagogical interventions or strategies that can help reduce language anxiety among APESA students. The following recommendations based on professors and students can be drawn from the study's results. For pedagogical intervention, instructors are recommended to:

- Implement different activities in the classroom. This can be done through adopting student-centered learning approaches. That is, instructors should give much attention and care to developing students' soft skills in addition to their linguistic ones.
- Creating a positive “trustworthy” environment between instructors and students and among students themselves where they can create a sense of self-belonging.
- Using “smart” techniques during the sessions such as drama, role play, theater, games, debates, spontaneous speaking activities...etc. These activities enhance students' engagement and participation without being anxious.
- Instructor's psychological factors impact students' engagement by reducing or boosting students' anxiety. In general, Instructors should be aware of students who suffer from FLA and their cultural background (many studies found that students' background is a significant variable that affects their language learning outcomes). Also, instructors try to demolish students' beliefs about exams and refrain from correcting their mistakes (fluency) because mistakes are seen as a part of the learning journey.
- Gradual exposure to public speaking commences with informal tasks and progresses to formal presentations, guaranteeing that students have sufficient practice time and receive constructive feedback to enhance their skills sustainably.
- Last, professional development opportunities will surely update them with solutions to address and tackle this issue smoothly.

The aforementioned pedagogical interventions and strategies aim to tackle factors that cause FLA and aid students with the necessary resources they need to succeed in their language learning journey. Students are also recommended to engage in any practical activities aimed at developing their self-confidence. To build their speaking skills and overcome their FLA, students are required to:

- Build self-confidence by starting with simple activities and moving upward to more challenging ones. This can be achieved by practicing regularly in and outside the classroom and not being afraid of making mistakes in front of their instructors or peers. They have to view mistakes as a part of the learning process and take them as opportunities to learn and not a failure.
- To develop a positive mindset, students need to focus on progress rather than perfection and never compare themselves with others.
- Taking into consideration that their instructor or teacher works for them and not against them. That is, the traditional notion of teaching sees the instructor or teacher as a symbol of authority while the new pedagogical teaching philosophy considers them as a facilitator who works for the students and not the opposite.

By implementing these strategies, students can manage and control their language learning process and work to mitigate their FLA. By identifying and addressing these distinct hurdles, APESA students can feel more empowered to traverse social contexts and academic surroundings with assurance and resilience.

Conclusion

FLA anxiety remains a significant barrier to speaking in the EFL context. The study underscores CA as the main trigger of anxiety among APESA students, followed by linguistic competence. The research study revealed the necessity for targeted pedagogical interventions and strategies not only to reduce students' anxiety but also to enhance their linguistic skills. Some practical solutions have been proposed based on the research's results to reduce FLA and aid students in being successful academically and in real-life communication.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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